

Boosting European Citizens' Knowledge and Awareness
of Bio-Economy Research and Innovation

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Bioeconomy mapping report

An overview of the bioeconomy

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Introduction

This deliverable is meant to give a starting point for BLOOM project to develop and disseminate implementation of the bioeconomy to European stakeholders, and develop regional hubs, by creating an overview of knowledge and insights, based on EU Research and Innovation, describing relevant issues of the bioeconomy. This deliverable contains 5 chapters:

1. Framework of the bioeconomy
2. A generalised technical overview of the bioeconomy
3. Framework of Concepts for transition
4. (Inter)national research, innovation and policies relevant to the bioeconomy
5. Concerns about bioeconomy development

The first chapter gives the reader the context in which the bioeconomy exists, the definition of bioeconomy and the challenges bioeconomy may contribute to. Also the relation to the climate problem will be brought forward. In the second chapter, a schematic overview of the bioeconomy is shown, describing feedstocks, conversion processes and bioeconomy products. This overview will be used further to describe activities in BLOOM hubs, and produce hub-specific dissemination material, to support implementation of the bioeconomy. The third chapter describes transition concepts which should be made operational to overcome organizational, economical and societal challenges. The fourth chapter gives an overview of Research and Innovation investment and the policies and strategies that have been adopted by the UN, EU and national/regional stakeholders. In the fifth chapter overarching concerns are described that are not related to a specific hub, but to implementation of the bioeconomy in general. These basics of Bioeconomy will be communicated, discussed and proceeded in the BLOOM activities, either in the Regional Hubs, the activities of the School Network and in BLOOM communication activities to the wider public.

1. Bioeconomy frame

1.1. Bioeconomy definition

The bioeconomy includes all biomass related applications and valorization routes, including human food and animal feed. There are multiple definitions in circulation: "A bioeconomy can be defined as an economy where the basic building blocks for materials, chemicals and energy are derived from renewable biological resources (McKinsey, 2013). The biobased economy is the part of the broader bioeconomy focussing on the transition from the use of fossil fuel to renewable biomass use in non-food applications. In the new Bioeconomy Strategy (2018) the EU defines bioeconomy as: "EU Bioeconomy Strategy":

The bioeconomy covers all sectors and systems that rely on biological resources (animals, plants, micro-organisms and derived biomass, including organic waste), their functions and principles. It includes and interlinks: land and marine ecosystems and the services they provide; all primary production sectors that use and produce biological resources (agriculture, forestry, fisheries and aquaculture); and all economic and industrial sectors that use biological resources and processes to produce food, feed, bio-based products, energy and services.

To be successful, the European bioeconomy needs to have sustainability and circularity at its heart. This will drive the renewal of our industries, the modernisation of our primary production systems, the protection of the environment and will enhance biodiversity. On the website² the EU addresses the goals for a Bioeconomy Strategy:

"Europe is setting course for a resource-efficient and sustainable economy. The goal is a more innovative and low-emissions economy, reconciling demands for sustainable agriculture and fisheries, food security, and the sustainable use of renewable biological resources for industrial purposes, while ensuring biodiversity and environmental protection".

To achieve this, the European Commission has set a Bioeconomy Strategy and an action plan that focuses on three key aspects:

- developing new technologies and processes for the bioeconomy;
- developing markets and competitiveness in bioeconomy sectors;
- pushing policymakers and stakeholders to work more closely together.

In his Agenda for Jobs, Growth, Fairness and Democratic Change, President Juncker identified 10 key priorities for the European Commission. The bioeconomy is central to three of them:

- **A new Boost for Jobs, Growth and Investment**

The innovative bioeconomy is an important source of new jobs – especially at local

² https://innovationsfonden.dk/sites/default/files/societal_readiness_levels_-_srl.pdf

and regional level, and in rural and coastal areas – and there are big opportunities for the growth of new markets, for example in bio-fuels, food and bio-based products.

- **A Resilient Energy Union with a Forward-Looking Climate Change Policy**
Europe needs to diversify its sources of energy and can support breakthroughs in low-carbon technologies with coordinated research. Replacing fossil raw materials with biological resources is an indispensable component of a forward-looking climate change policy.
- **A Deeper and Fairer Internal Market with a Strengthened Industrial Base**
Innovative bio-based and food industries will contribute in raising the share of industry in GDP from 16% to 20% and to creating a circular, resource-efficient economy. The food and drink industry is already the largest manufacturing sector in the EU.

In addition, marine issues and food security are two aspects of the bioeconomy where Europe can and should lead the global agenda as part of President Juncker's strategy to make the EU a stronger global actor.”

1.2. Bioeconomy and the Climate problem

The climate challenge is the foremost reason why bioeconomy gains attention. The biobased economy contributes to mitigating climate change with various techniques, ranging from very simple such as re-using a waste stream from one process as feedstock in another, to very complex like building new materials such as bioplastics from fractions (or components) of the original biomass. The aim is always to maximize the efficiency of material flows, especially of carbon. In the production process and during transport of various products carbon is burned to meet the energy requirements, and those requirements vary with the products and the applied techniques. Carbon can be captured in constructions based on biomass fibres such as wood for a long time and even at its end of life the wood can serve as fuel to offset fossil fuel. A specific biomass feedstock can be used to produce many different products when it is into separate components. The total amount of CO₂ used in specific processes and products, i.e. the carbon footprint, can be estimated with so-called lifecycle assessments (LCA). However, for new processes or processes under development there is a lack of reliable data, which makes comparison with established processes sometimes difficult.

An economy founded on biomass instead of fossil resources represents a significant shift in socio-economic, agricultural, energy and technical systems. Regions and countries need better information and participation of the general public, including all potential stakeholders in existing and new/modified value chains (farmers, SMEs, consumers,

consumer associations, environmental NGOs, media, waste collectors and converters, citizens, schools and public services etc.). Raising the awareness on the positive effects of the bioeconomy and a circular economy is an important goal in several projects and/or strategies. In order to promote new products that are more bio-based, it is necessary to generate understanding, social acceptance and support among the general public and to assure quality and availability of the new products. A lack of popularisation of Research and Innovation activities in the region and science communication with the general public is thus leading to insufficient awareness of the population (and businesses) of the region and elsewhere.

Figure 1 presents an overview of the domain in which the biobased economy operates. The main reason why the biobased economy is so high on the agenda nowadays is that existing practices contribute to serious climate problems. Continuation of fossil resource consumption brings more and more carbon dioxide in the atmosphere which contributes to the well-known greenhouse effect. Up until now it has been proven unfeasible to bring back the carbon (at least in large quantities) to the deep earth layers where it came from. The IPCC is concerned that without adequate action earth temperatures will rise with more than 2 °C by the year 2050 posing numerous environmental threats. The climate problem has to be seen as a so-called grand challenge, recognized by the EU (Esir, 2017) and most other nations in the Paris agreement.

Biobased Economy Environment

Figure 1 Overview of the Biobased economy environment

While the climate issue constitutes a major problem, there are many other good reasons to reconsider the use of biomass and the way in which it is produced, converted and transported to consumers, including environmental protection and social inclusion as mentioned by Juncker in the key priorities.

In order to prevent worst case scenarios from happening (in all scenarios there is considerable damage anyway, and therefore calling for adaptation strategies) there are basically three routes for climate change mitigation.

1. Prevent further use of fossil resources
2. Carbon Capture & Storage (CCS)
3. Enhance the carbon cycle and capture more carbon in the living biosphere (including living organisms in the top-soil layer) and in the Soil Organic Matter pool) e.g. greenhouses to combat greenhouse gases (In greenhouses up to 16 t/ha/yr C can be captured)

The biobased economy mainly focuses on the first strategy, i.e. to replace the use of fossil resources for materials production with renewable biomass. The potential role of the biobased economy in this strategy is substantial. According to a recent Dutch study on creating 'negative emissions' (Strengers et al, 2018), 17 to 19% of the technical potential and more than 30% of the realistic practical potential to create negative emissions in the

Netherlands by the year 2050 can be allocated towards the biobased economy (chemical and the green concrete routes).

However, when applying this strategy, the innovative biobased solutions compete with existing practices. Obviously the biobased solutions need to perform better on climate related issues than the existing practices; otherwise they would not be accepted as solutions. However, it is sometimes difficult for new processes to compete with established and mature technology, also in terms of climate impact. Improvement of climate performance is therefore an important focus for the further development of new bio-based technologies. But climate change is not the only impact at stake. There can be numerous other impacts on other relevant issues for the bioeconomy stakeholders, for instance on jobs or on profit for shareholders. The 'climate gain' of the biobased solution is weighed against the impacts of other changes by the stakeholders. This involves complex social processes which are addressed by a framework of transition concepts.

2. General technological concept of the bioeconomy

This chapter gives an overview of the resources, processes and products that are produced in the bioeconomy. It aims to be generic and fully inclusive. For each European region, and the regional hubs as defined in the BLOOM project, different aspects of this overview will be relevant. In the BLOOM project, the bioeconomy overview for each hub will be defined in further detail, to facilitate tailor-made dissemination per hub. This gives BLOOM a tool to show where the hubs strength lies, what and how to communicate to stakeholders, and where they may develop their bioeconomy further.

2.1. The concept

Figure 2 describes the carbon flows through the bioeconomy, starting in the centre with photosynthesis. It contains Biorefineries (yellow blocks), where incoming streams are separated into multiple other streams, and factories where incoming streams are converted to (intermediate) products (purple blocks). In grey, intermediate and end products are defined. These processes and products are explained in more detail in chapter 2.1. The arrows describe streams of feedstocks, intermediate products, products and residues. A detailed description is shown in chapter 2.2. Figure 2 depicts the entire bioeconomy – on the left side a food factory, where food and feed production and their recycling are included. The biobased economy is shown at the top part of the figure, at the non-food factory. The value chains start with growing biomass from sunlight and CO₂ through photosynthesis. The next step is fractionation and conversion within refineries, and further processing and valorization in biobased products in non-food industries. Certain products, especially chemicals and materials, can be reused; eventually, all products are combusted into energy and CO₂, where the cycle restarts. In chapter 2.3 the potential of various bio-based value chains is presented.

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Figure 2.1 General overview of the bioeconomy

2.2. Description of processes

This chapter explains the processing steps that occur in the biobased value chains (shown as yellow, purple and grey blocks in Figure 2.1). Descriptions are short and general, to include the entire bioeconomy.

Photosynthesis

Photosynthesis is a process used by plants and other organisms to convert light energy into chemical energy that can later be released to fuel the organisms' activities (energy transformation). This chemical energy is stored in carbohydrate molecules, such as sugars, which are synthesized from carbon dioxide and water.

For related topic see: <http://edepot.wur.nl/353079>

Wood

Woody biomass like logs, branches etc.

Terrestrial crops

Mainly agricultural crops like corn, wheat, potatoes, sugar beets, olives, grapes etc. For further reading, see <http://edepot.wur.nl/291817>

Aquatic biomass

Microalgae, macroalgae, and fresh water plants

Harvest

Harvesting of biomass, often combined with mechanical separation.

Biorefinery (1) raw material

In the first biorefinery, harvested biomass is separated into several (intermediate) products for applications in food (**arrow 6**, e.g. starches, oils, flour) and non-food (**arrow 5**, e.g. starches, paper pulp, sugars, oils). Part of the biomass returns back to agricultural land as fertilizer (**arrow 7**). This Biorefinery includes also a papermill producing pulp and lignin for energy purposes.

Biorefinery (2) residues

Processing of used cooking oils into biodiesel, of human-based sources ((e.g. garden waste, faeces) in composting installations and wastewater treatments) and animal-based sources (manure) to Energy (2) (**arrow 15**) and back to land (**arrow 12**) as soil improvement and fertilizer.

Biorefinery (3) animal

Processing of animal-based sources for food (**arrow 16**, e.g. milk, meat, gelatine) and non-food applications (**arrow 14**, e.g. tallow, skins, bone meal). Residues and manure to [Biorefinery \(2\) residues](#).

Thermal conversion factory

Processing of whole biomass to produce inputs for the **Non-food Factory**. Processes include combustion (heat and electricity), gasification (heat, electricity, syngas, SNG), pyrolysis (biochar and pyrolysis oil), torrefaction (biomass pellets for combustion).

Recycling

Recycling facilities for conversion of used end-products to new raw materials for non-food factory (e.g. paper, plastic bottles, textiles) (arrow 32).

Combustion

All product streams not suitable for recycling (arrows 25 and 33) go to combustion to generate heat and electricity (arrow 26)

Mechanical wood processing

Processing of wood by sawing to mainly beams, planks and sawdust.

Food factory

Processing of intermediate biomass components into food (main output) and feed (residual stream) end-products.

Non-food factory

Conversion of all kinds of biomass components to multiple non-food products. Chemical, biochemical and mechanical processes.

End-product factory

Production of end products (textiles, building materials, plastics, furniture etc)

2.3. Explanation of flows

Table 1 gives a concise overview of the (intermediate) product and residue streams that are shown as arrows in Figure 2. Streams are defined broadly, as to contain the entire bioeconomy.

Table 1: Explanation of streams in Figure 3, describing the bioeconomy

Arrow nr.	Description
1	Whole biomass transported to Biorefinery (1) Raw material for further processing
2	Harvested crops for feed (e.g. maize)
3	Harvested crops for food, ready to eat like vegetables, fruit.
4	Harvested biomass for thermal conversion as feedstock for non-food factory
5	Biomass components (e.g. starch, oil, cellulose (pulp), lignin, sugars) from Refinery (1) raw material to be converted to non-food products (chemicals, materials, fuels and energy).
6	Intermediates for Food Factory (e.g. starches, oils, flour)
7	Residual streams from Biorefinery (1) Raw material going back to the land as soil improver or fertilizer.
8	Processed food products for human consumption
9	Residual streams coming from the food industry for feed applications (e.g. brewers spent grain, beet pulp)
10	Animal products (e.g. milk, meat, bones, skins, manure) as input for Biorefinery (3) animal
11	Used cooking oil, Human waste and garden waste to Biorefinery (2) residues
12	Digestate and compost back to land
13	Electricity and heat produced from residues that are not suitable for other applications Biorefinery (1) Raw material.
14	Animal-based feedstocks (tallow, skins, bone meal) to Non-food Factory
15	Electricity and heat produced from residues that are not suitable for other applications, biodiesel produced from used cooking oil Biorefinery (2) Residues
16	Animal-based products to Food Factory like milk, meat, bones for gelatin.
17	Manure to Biorefinery (2) Residues
18	Pyrolysis oil to Non-food Factory
19	Green chemical building blocks produced in Non-food Factory (e.g. lactic acid, succinic acid etc). For further reading, see https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/bbb.1468

20	Green chemicals and polymeric materials produced in Non-food Factory for material production
21	Residues from Non-food Factory for energy applications (heat and electricity) and biofuels produced by chemical and biochemical (fermentation) technologies from mainly sugars and vegetable oils.
22	Chemicals to End-product Factory
23	Materials to End-product Factory
24	End-products suitable for recycling
25	End-products not suitable for recycling and to be converted by combustion to electricity and heat
26	Energy (electricity and heat) from combustion of end-products
27	Wood from forestry to Mechanical wood processing
28	Products from Mechanical wood processing like beams and planks for furniture, building materials, construction materials.
29	Residues from Mechanical wood processing to be converted to electricity and heat
30	Wood-based materials suitable for recycling to e.g. materials, or board applications.
31	Wood-based materials after use for Combustion to electricity and heat
32	Recycled resources (chemical building blocks and/or materials) as input for Non-Food Factory
33	Residues from recycling for Combustion to electricity and heat

2.4. Potential of biobased value chains

The type of biomass and its properties and composition largely determine for what application and in which of many possible bioeconomy value chains it is suitable. Below, some main properties are briefly expanded upon; to give the reader an idea of their influence on the biomass' application possibilities of biomass in the various value chains is dependent on the biomass properties and composition.

Moisture content

Broadly speaking, most biomass with high moisture content (such as potatoes, sugar beets, algae, grass etc.) is applied in food production processes, although water may be removed during processing. Side streams, or in some cases the main products, can be used for feed production or fermentative production of food and chemicals.

Moisture content is very well suited to be use in fermentation processes, or (anaerobic) digestion. Transportation and long term storage of biomass with a high moisture content, however is relatively costly and difficult.

Biomass with a low moisture content (such as woody materials or vegetable oil, sawdust, vegetable oil, straw etc.) may preferably be applied in chemical processes where water would be problematic, such as biodiesel production or thermochemical processes like is well

suited for application in thermochemical processes, such as pyrolysis, gasification and combustion.

Density

A high biomass density, in combination with a low moisture content is beneficial for transport and handling in general. Pellets of wood, grass or straw, wood, vegetable oil, sugar and grain, and also intermediate products such as pyrolysis oil and ethanol, are all examples of high density biomass. Straw, leaves and bagasse have a lower density.

Carbohydrate content

Carbohydrate rich feedstock, such as cereals and sugar beet are an important basis for our food. Next to that carbohydrates are also important feedstock for chemical conversions and fermentation. Products and intermediates that can be produced from carbohydrates are for instance ethanol, butanol, lactic acid (for the production of the biodegradable bioplastic polylactic acid, PLA), succinic acid (for the production of the biodegradable bioplastic PBS). Cellulose is also a carbohydrate and can form the feedstock for chemical conversions and fermentations. Cellulose is a so-called second generation feedstock and needs to be converted first into smaller sugar molecules, before it can be fermented or chemically converted.

Protein content

Proteins are first and foremost important as food and feed. For digestion and fermentation processes a small amount of protein in the feedstock can be beneficial. However, for thermochemical processes and combustion proteins are unwanted due to the formation of ammonia and nitrogen oxides that have a negative environmental impact and can affect materials. For instance grass, oil-rich seeds, microalgae and cereals are rich in protein.

Fibres

Wood, grass and straw are composed of fibrous structures, from cellulose, hemicellulose and lignin. They can be used in material applications where this structure is beneficial, such as paper, board and building materials. Specific fibre crops, such as cotton, hemp and flax contain long fibres that can be used in textiles and composite construction materials.

Vegetable oil

Vegetable oil is an important ingredient for food, but has also established applications in chemistry for the production of soaps and surfactants and as ingredient for paints. Vegetable oil can also be used for biodiesel. Oil rich crops are for instance oilpalm, sunflower, rapeseed. Also used cooking oil can be used for the production of biodiesel and chemicals.

Mineral content

Minerals are disturbing for thermochemical and combustion processes. Biochemical processes such as fermentation and digestion are less sensitive to mineral content. Mineral rich biomass is for instance manure, straw, grass, sugar beet and seaweed.

The value chains

Bioeconomy value chains can thus consist of varying partners and technologies, dependent on the feedstock they are based upon. As is also clear from figure 2, biorefineries are often at the heart of the value chains. An overview of biorefineries in Europe in 2017, is generated by nova Institute and presented in figure 2.2. These biorefineries are integrated production plants using biomass or biomass-derived feedstock to produce a range of value-added (non-food) products and energy.

Biorefineries in Europe 2017

Figure 2.2. Overview of biorefineries in Europe, focusing on non-food products. (source nova Institute)

Most of the wood-based biorefineries are located in the Nordic countries, whereas in Western-Europe sugar/starch (carbohydrates) and vegetable oil based refineries are abundant, which is also reflected by the focus of the Nordic and western European BLOOM hubs.

The bio-based industries consortium and nova Institute estimate the total turnover of the bioeconomy in EU-28 to be 2.28 trillion euro in 2015, of which about 2/3 is generated in agriculture and the food and beverages industries, and 1/3 by the non-food markets such as

paper and board, forest based products, biofuel/bioenergy and chemicals and plastics (see figure 2.3).

Turnover in the bioeconomy in the EU-28, 2008-2015

Figure 2.3 Turnover in the bioeconomy in various markets (source BBI and nova Institute)

Nova Insitute (nova Institute 2018) expects a large growth for especially the chemicals and plastics sector in Europe up to the year 2023, with production capacity for bioplastics growing from 8 Mtonnes in 2018 to 9.6 Mtonnes in 2023, and production capacities for bio-based building blocks growing from about 2.5 Mtonnes in 2018 to 3.1 Mtonnes in 2023. Most of these technologies are based on carbohydrate feedstock.

Obviously these new markets offer a large potential for bioeconomy value chains. Bioeconomy value chains, however, often consist of different partners coming from different sectors, such as agriculture and agri-food industry and chemical industry. Setting up successful value chains between partners from different backgrounds is not easy. In the next chapter we will elaborate on the steps and actions that need to be taken in order to fully develop these promising new bioeconomy value chains.

3. Framework of transition concepts

This chapter identifies 6 overarching concepts that are needed to manage the complex problems that come with the transition toward a bioeconomy. This framework defines critical issues to address during implementation of the bioeconomy and it will be used during co-creation workshops as background for discussion.

The complexity of the bioeconomy is many times mentioned in the 3rd bioeconomy Stakeholder meeting in Torino. Bioeconomy is seen as a game changer, with a need for integrated approach towards the generation of new innovative products. The creation of new biobased value chain developments is to be seen as a complex problem, especially regarding the EU biobased landscape (small scale), characteristics, specific objectives and frameworks. The following dimensions can be distinguished:

- cross-sectoral: connecting different sectors: new value chains to be developed from biomass production to biobased products between agricultural sector with the chemical or energy, construction or materials industries etc.
- triple helix interplay: business, research and government and extension with the Civil Society towards a quadruple helix collaboration. This means connecting different domains (public, private, society and knowledge) with their own values, cultures and languages.
- cross-regional value chain development, connect regions with biomass availability to regions with processing facilities, industries, knowledge centres; bringing together knowledge, capacities and investments.
- cross-disciplinary (natural and human science; plant science, biobased, environmental and economic research) and valorization of knowledge (fundamental research, applied research; education and innovation)
- integrated approach: economy, climate, energy, biodiversity, food security; technological, organizational, financial and cultural challenge

To deal with complexity of different partners, cultures, perspectives, disciplines, domains and phases in the development processes, suitable management concepts and techniques are needed. These concepts offer conditions for innovations, collaborations and investments, to and allow the ability to steer, manage and coordinate the deployment of bioeconomy in European regions.

Next to the complexity of the bioeconomy, in the execution of new strategies and policies, different gaps between current practices and biobased solutions are being identified, which hamper the uptake of the bioeconomy in Europe.

Within universities and research centres there has been conducted technological research for years on the potential of crops and crop components for other applications than food or feed, often financed by EU RTD in framework programmes of Research and Innovation. The research community together with some business partners have developed and tested

technologies such as biorefinery techniques to convert the plant components to building blocks for chemistry, energy and other valorization routes. Currently, there is a gap between the technology development and the awareness of potential value chain partners and the general public, which hampers a larger uptake. The current uptake is characterised by small scale pilots and demos. There is still limited demand for biobased resources, building blocks or products, both within the value chain as at the end of the value chain, from consumers. Biobased products are only very limited available. Products seem to be not better or cheaper than regular equivalents of oil based products, often due to still immature technology and small scale production lines and volumes.

According to Hekkert (2015) transitions do face lock-in problems, such as resistance, current business practices, conflicting interest (Hekkert, 2015). Klikou (2015) adds learning effects, economies of scale, economies of scope, network externalities, informational increasing returns, technological interrelatedness, collective action, institutional learning effects and the differentiation of power.

To overcome the gaps and to deal with lock-in situations, theory, concepts and frameworks which deal with complexity and to manage the transition to a bioeconomy should be made operational. Six interacting concepts have been identified that offer information about patterns of and phases in the development process, and offer organisational basics about conditions for innovation and instruments to stimulate and support the transition and to arrive to well performing regional bioeconomy innovations systems. The following concepts are distinguished and illustrated in Figure 3:

- Clusters: spatial (appearance of new industrial sites, new biomass production activities, new crops or new valorization facilities, collection points of biomass and conversion sites; fragmentation vs clustering, economies of scale) and organizational (from network to innovation ecosystem)
- Regional innovation strategies of smart specialization (RIS3)
 - Triple and quadruple helix
 - Entrepreneurial discovery
- Value chain management – connection of biomass producers, refineries and industries
- Readiness
 - Technological innovations in search of new value chains
 - Social: awareness and understanding of the value of biobased innovations and products, ethical issues
- Circular Economy: the principles behind circular economy and the routes to (re) use and valorise waste streams
- Innovation pipeline: from fundamental knowledge to applied knowledge, piloting and demonstration and to investment, business case development and upscaling

Framework of concepts

Figure 3 Framework of concepts to address bioeconomy social issues

In Figure 3 the six interacting concepts are displayed that are relevant for proceeding biobased innovations and transitions towards more sustainable societies.

Within the concepts the following processes, labelled as ‘functions of innovation systems’ are relevant (Hekkert, 2015):

- Supply incentives for companies to engage in innovative work
- Supply resources (capital and competence)
- Guide the direction of search (influence the direction in which actors deploy—resources)
- Recognize the potential for growth (identifying technological possibilities and economic viability)
- Facilitate the exchange of information and knowledge
- Stimulate/create markets
- Reduce social uncertainty (i.e., uncertainty about how others will act and react)
- Counteract the resistance to change that may arise in society when an innovation is introduced (provide legitimacy for the innovation) (Heckert, 2015).

3.1. Clusters

Clusters can be seen as a conceptual framework to analyse the economic performances of regions and industries. Clusters can also be seen as conceptual framework for designing and managing economic activities at specific locations.

Clusters, understood as co-located activities in related industries connected through different types of linkages and externalities, are a naturally emerging feature of market economies (Ketels, 2015). Clusters might also be associated with a specific type of competitive behaviour by companies that can be summarized as a 'high road'-strategy. In facing customers, high-road strategies are characterized by a focus on value through high quality and unique features. In production, high-road strategies are characterized by investments in internal assets such as the capital stock, skills and technology. They often also have an external dimension as companies work with their suppliers and service providers in upgrading their respective capabilities, and in jointly developing innovations. These investments are likely to generate positive spill-overs that reinforce the cluster through deepening the local supply of specialized skills and adding to the available knowledge stock. In parallel, the presence of the cluster is likely to provide an environment in which companies will find the external inputs that make opting for high-road strategies more likely; they will be able to access the advanced skills and supplies needed. Regions with a strong presence of clusters are those more likely to settle in an equilibrium where a sufficient majority of companies choose high-road' strategies (Ketels, 2015).

Clusters seem to be an interesting concept, as this offers spatial, organizational and energetic efficiencies, which will offer conditions for biobased industries in general and bio chemical production in particular. Industrial clustering and industrial symbiosis, based on the principles of the circular economy, should be explored and potentially promoted as an aid to the more effective utilisation of knowledge, resources and infrastructure in developing the bio-economy (IEEP, 2015).

Clusters represent regional hotspots in *networks* which are:

- a necessary infrastructure in modern society for various actors (from government, civil society and business) to interact with each other
- probably important steering mechanisms in economic and social decision making and incentivising (perhaps even more important than markets and all kind of hierarchies within society)
- channels for transport of knowledge

Cluster development can be strengthened by policies, regional innovation management and entrepreneurial strategic decisions, instruments and investments. The EU Regional Innovation Strategies of Smart Specialization form a good framework to explore the opportunities and the comparative advantages and to make steps in the regional development pathway. France has developed clusters (*pôles de compétitivité*) since the early 2000's. The IAR cluster in France is to be seen as a good practice bioeconomy cluster (Berst, 2015):

IAR Cluster (North of France) has successfully developed an integrated organisation structure which facilitates the active involvement of regional partners across sectors. In detail, the following issues have been observed during the three development stages:

- The initial stage comprised of the establishment of a network that served as the basis for interactions and collaborations with regional partners, fifteen farmer cooperatives and the local agro- industry. The network applied the triple helix concept and its activities focused on raising awareness and developing a common strategy.
- The drive to maturity stage focused on the establishment of collaborative initiatives and creating crossovers between the agricultural and other sectors as well as familiarising with the capabilities of the cluster partners and creating synergies among them through applying for funding under common initiatives, such as:
 - Investments in R&D, pilots and demo's to "overcome the valley of death" and come to de-risking. During that stage more almost 200 R&D projects have been approved. All initiatives from IAR consortia and cluster partners, focused on strengthening the cluster and progressing in biobased value chain development are being evaluated and approved by the IAR cluster organisation. One of the eligibility criteria has been that an application always has to be submitted by three organisations.
 - Creation of labs, pilot plants, large investments in equipment, with priority at commonly shared facilities to be of use also for other companies, even from outside the regions. So far there are three of these open facilities: sugar, lipids and protein.
 - Augmentation of the network by attracting and integrating new companies from potential value chains, some of them outside the region.
- During the mature stage the cluster focuses on 'making it happen' by:
 - Finding new business opportunities: facilitation of technological business partnerships, help in accelerating the value chain development.
 - Expanding innovation dynamics: optimizing and animating the working groups - enlarging the EU horizon.
 - Integrating new partners: international outreach of the network, strategic partnerships, exploration of export potential of knowledge and technologies, developed in the cluster.
 - Attracting investment.

3.2. Regional Innovation Strategy of Smart Specialization

The European Smart Specialisation Strategy: "Research and Innovation strategies for Smart Specialisation" or **RIS3** initiated by the European think tank (ERA) can also be seen in this context. Rather than following each lead, regional cluster organisations should focus on a few integrated value chains at most in order to avoid - or at least minimize - regional fragmentation of initiatives. The EU Regional Innovation Strategies of Smart Specialization (RIS3) has the objective to make optimally use of regional strengths and opportunities and the regional comparative advantages - location factors do matter a lot. Entrepreneurial Discovery process (EDP) is an inclusive and interactive bottom-up process in which

participants from different environments (policy, business, academia – so called triple helix partners) are discovering and producing information about potential new activities, identifying potential opportunities that emerge through this interaction, while policymakers assess outcomes and ways to facilitate the realisation of this potential. The EDP pursues the integration of entrepreneurial knowledge fragmented and distributed over many sites and organisations, companies, universities, clients and users, specialised suppliers (some of these entities being located outside of the region) through the building of connections and partnerships. The EDP consists of the exploration and opening up of a new domain of opportunities (technological and market), potentially rich in numerous innovations that emerge as feasible and attractive. This process leads also to strengthen regional profile. A regional profile is a **configuration** of:

- physical characteristics, economical structure, infrastructure
- type of bioregion, chain, function/position within the wider bio economy landscape and with specific crossovers between biomass production and converting industries
- organizational structure, governance, network, support structure and services
- strategy: vision, development path, short term/long term, instruments and measures

Regional profile has an **external** effect in which competitive advantages are shown with marketing instruments to attract attention of new businesses, investments and funding. Regional profile has an **internal** effect in strategic decision making of partner organizations, which helps to focus and clarifies future objectives. The profile creates communality and connectedness and mobilizes people and organizations along the lines of strategic decisions, to create a support infrastructure and new intermediates in triple helix. It also creates new dynamics in the entrepreneurial discovery process.

3.3. Integrated Value Chain

The integrated value chain is a logical chain of partners working together to add value to primary biomass in several steps and to look for synergies in production pipelines. To connect the agro production and to new processing industries is rather complex, due to different cultures, networks and scales. Value chain management will optimally bring together partners, connect or integrate VC partners which can add value to resources and products.

In many EU regions, there are opportunities for biobased production. The availability of biomass is precondition number 1. As Europe does not have a large scale biomass production like in the USA, EU should search for optimal concepts and appearance of biobased industries and added value activities within their regions. Transport costs still determine to a large extent the optimal location of bioeconomy facilities. Therefore pre-treatment at the farm level may lead to increase the income of farmers and to decrease the transportation costs, because less water, and therefore mass, will be transported.

The second local factor seems to be the presence of processing industries, such as agricultural cooperations and industries and chemical industries (forward integration) or

the presence of a petrochemical refinery plot, which could be turned into a biochemical refinery (backward integration).

- Corn ethanol plants: CO₂ selling, novel proteins, integrated process, many side streams – cluster biorefineries with side facilities
- Cost competitiveness of sugar beets – high yields in NW-Europe. The Netherlands is a good location.
- Strong chemical industry – searching nowadays for new synergies
- Use of existing biorefineries, pilot plants or large new production locations? use of production facilities of existing industries (for example pulp, pre-treatment, CO₂ availability)

Next to these preconditions, a wide network of business partners with all kind of services is needed to come to full production, as well as buyers of bio chemical building blocks, as packaging industry and end users as commercial brand owners. Also governments, knowledge institutes, financial institutes play important roles in the bio economy transition process.

3.4. Innovation Pipeline and Readiness

The **innovation pipeline** represents a logical order by which innovations usually evolve. Innovation starts with ideation. Promising ideas will be explored by scoping the potential of these ideas. The next phase is characterised by testing the innovation often in lab settings or at pilot scale, and demonstrating it to decision makers and investors. Then the business case will be elaborated and implemented. All phases of innovation need different support services, as finance, knowledge, capacities and facilities.

Transitions from one phase to the next don't always run smooth. The so called valley of death often occurs when innovations have reached and passed the demo phase. Then all of a sudden the most difficult part, reaching maturity, has yet to come. It is important to recognize these hurdles in advance and to be prepared to go through the innovation process as smooth as possible and set up an optimal innovation support system.

That's also where **readiness** levels come in. Technological readiness levels (TRL) were recognized by the European Commission in 2014 (EC, 2014). The primary purpose of using technology readiness levels is to help management in making decisions concerning the development and transitioning of technology. It should be viewed as one of several tools that are needed to manage the progress of research and development activity within an organization (can also be a cluster or a region). There are nine TRL levels .

Where a topic description refers to a TRL, the following definitions apply (EC, 2014):

1. TRL 1 – basic principles observed
2. TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
3. TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
4. TRL 4 – technology validated in lab
5. TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)

6. TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment (industrially relevant environment in the case of key enabling technologies)
7. TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment
8. TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
9. TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment (competitive manufacturing in the case of key enabling technologies; or in space)

Next to the technology development and implementation, innovations have also social implications, regarding societal acceptance and the societal uptake of the innovation. It involves topics/issues such as awareness raising, knowledge transfer, coalition building, addressing and coping with resistance (lock-ins) (e.g. by compensating for real losses instead of just enforcing new realities), trust building, institutionalizing new practices. All TRL phases have equivalent Societal Readiness Levels (SRL), which “is a way of assessing the level of societal adaptation of, for instance, a particular social project, a technology, a product, a process, an intervention, or an innovation (whether social or technical) to be integrated into society”². Additionally Wenger (1998) emphasizes that with social instruments, the social aspects of innovations can be supported and managed.

Besides the innovation pipeline and the readiness levels the

3.5. Circular economy

Recently, in the last 5 years, the concept of circular economy has become highly relevant for bioeconomy and therefore BLOOM. In January 2012, a report entitled “Towards the Circular Economy: Economic and business rationale for an accelerated transition”(2012) was released, commissioned by the Ellen MacArthur Foundation and developed by McKinsey & Company. It was the first report to consider the economic and business opportunity for the transition to a restorative, circular model. Using product case studies and economy-wide analysis, the report details the potential for significant benefits across the EU. It argues that a subset of the EU manufacturing sector could realise net materials cost savings worth up to \$630 billion annually towards 2025—stimulating economic activity in the areas of product development, remanufacturing and refurbishment. Towards the Circular Economy also identified the key building blocks in making the transition to a circular economy, namely in skills in circular design and production, new business models, skills in building cascades and reverse cycles, and cross-cycle/cross-sector collaboration.

A circular economy is a regenerative system in which resource input and waste, emission, and energy leakage are minimised by slowing, closing, and narrowing energy and material loops. This can be achieved through long-lasting design, maintenance, repair, reuse, remanufacturing, refurbishing, and recycling. This is in contrast to a linear economy which is a 'take, make, dispose' model of production. (McArthur Foundation, 2012), as shown in Figure 4.

² https://innovationsfonden.dk/sites/default/files/societal_readiness_levels_-_srl.pdf

OUTLINE OF A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

PRINCIPLE

1

Preserve and enhance natural capital by controlling finite stocks and balancing renewable resource flows
ReSOLVE levers: regenerate, virtualise, exchange

PRINCIPLE

2

Optimise resource yields by circulating products, components and materials in use at the highest utility at all times in both technical and biological cycles
ReSOLVE levers: regenerate, share, optimise, loop

PRINCIPLE

3

Foster system effectiveness by revealing and designing out negative externalities
All ReSOLVE levers

1. Hunting and fishing
2. Can take both post-harvest and post-consumer waste as an input
Source: Ellen MacArthur Foundation, SUN, and McKinsey Center for Business and Environment; Drawing from Braungart & McDonough, Cradle to Cradle (C2C).

Figure 4 the outline of the Circular Economy (Ella MacArthur Foundation, 2012)

Knowing the concept of the possible routes for re-use and valorisation of waste and biomass, regional networks or the partners should use this conceptual information to manage, facilitate or support the uptake of the circular economy. The general idea is to use available biomass resources and nutrients efficient, i.e. at low non-renewable carbon costs and to move carbon from the atmosphere to other pools (such as the biosphere- and the top-soil layers). This can be achieved for instance by keeping nutrient cycles as local as possible, by lengthening the lifetime of physical products or subtracting from the use of fossil feedstock's. The latter method is the most important aim of many biobased solutions. In order to monitor the impact (evidence base) life cycle inventories are set-up as a part of the new economy, also to support actors such as businesses with their transition towards circular business models.

4. Bioeconomy Research, Innovation and Policies

4.1. EU Bioeconomy Research and Innovation

The first European programme on biotechnology (1982 – 1986) run by the European Commission (Aguilar et al, 2012) started even before the first framework programme (1984 - 1987). The term bioeconomy was not in use at the time and the focus of the programme was indeed on the biotechnological aspects and development (Aguilar et al, 2012).

4.1.1. Period FP6 (2002 – 2006)

Total framework budget 16.3 bln , of which 0.4 – 0.6 bln (2.5% -3.5%) related to bioeconomy. In the budgetary periods before the 6th framework programme the R&D budget gradually increased to around 400 to 600 million over the five year period of the 6th programme, depending on which sectors are recognized as part of the bioeconomy. With respect to this categorization a colour scheme was adopted to distinct various aspects of the bioeconomy: red (health biotechnology), green (plant and environmental biotechnology), blue (marine biotechnology) and white (industrial biotechnology). Later on the term grey biotechnology was introduced (separated from white) for technological solutions created to protect the environment and also modern biotechnology to distinguish newer applications of biotechnology (McCormick and Kautto, 2013). For our understanding of the relative importance of the bioeconomy sector on should realize that the definition of bioeconomy, i.e. what has to be included content-wise, is rather fluid over the years.

In a recent article Ronzon and M'Barek (2018) listed only primary and manufacturing sectors (plus the production of bioenergy) as part of the bioeconomy, some of them even as a hybrid. This excludes all service sectors with possible activities related to the bioeconomy such as wholesale, retail, transport, repair and recycling, advise and research from being part of the bioeconomy.

Biotechnology in the 6th programme was almost exclusively focused on human health (Aguilar et al, 2012). Despite this narrow focus the first European strategy for biotechnology, which had a broad scope, was launched in 2002. The dialogue with stakeholders, policy development and research planning and management moved from being fragmented and uncoordinated to being interdependent (Aguilar et al, 2012). Life sciences and biotechnology were brought in convergence with other technologies. The objective was to provide a knowledge base management, products and use of biological resources. Although the terms bioeconomy or circular economy were not mentioned, the strategy culminated in the development of the knowledge based Bio-Economy in Europe (KBBE) concept towards the end of the 6th framework period.

Timeline key events:

2002: Life Sciences and Biotechnology. A Strategy for Europe. COM(2002)27 - January 2002

- Biotechnology has the potential to improve non-food uses of crops as sources of industrial feedstocks or new materials such as biodegradable plastics
- Biomass may contribute to alternative energy sources ...such as biodiesel and bioethanol.

- Biotech may lead to the development of cleaner industrial products and processes using enzymes (biocatalysis)

2002 – 2006: Creation of 7 Technology Platforms relevant to the KBBE, 10 relevant ERA-NETs
 2006: Launch of KBBE-Net (March 2006). Focus is on the knowledge base of bioeconomy. The term bioeconomy includes all industries and economic sectors that produces, manages or otherwise exploit biological resources. The market size in the EU at the time is estimated at € trillion turnover, and over 22 mln people involved (5% of the population).

4.1.2. Period FP7 (2007 -2013)

Total framework budget 50.5 bln, of which 1.76 – 1.9 bln (3,5% - 3.8%) related to bioeconomy

The 7th framework programme acknowledged nine thematic priorities. The second one was about Food, Agriculture and Biotechnology. The highlights were addressed in a power point from the EU-US Biotechnology Taskforce (2010):

- Policy-makers, governments, industry, public and private research
 - bodies, civil society to recognise the potential of life science and biotechnology and discuss a framework for growth;
- Establish a regulatory, institutional and societal environment
 - supportive of a bio-economy;
- Demonstrate clear benefits for the consumer;
- Incentives to exploit its benefits in terms of competitiveness,
 - environmental compatibility and potential for rural development;
- Participants in the chain – farmers, industry, regulators and
 - consumers – need to get together to actually make the bioeconomy work.

The research objectives were also pointed out:

- Strengthen the knowledge base, deliver the innovations and provide policy support for building and developing a European Knowledge Based Bio-Economy (KBBE);
- Respond to social and economic challenges:
 - Sustainable agriculture/fishery and climate change
 - Clean biomaterials from renewable bio-resources
 - High quality food and sustainable food production
 - Food-related disorders (cardiovascular, obesity ...)
 - Infectious animal diseases and zoonoses
- Involve all stakeholders (incl. industry) in research
- Support CAP and CFP
- Respond quickly to emerging research needs

The KBBE which was launched at the end of the 6th framework provided for mission oriented pilot and demonstration projects (Aguilar et al, 2012). In 2012, towards the end of the budgetary period, the European Commission launched the second bioeconomy strategy proposing a comprehensive approach to address the ecological, environmental, energy, food supply and natural resource challenges. In 2013, following a public online consultation the European Commission produced a report on the advantages of developing a European strategy on a sustainable bio-based economy. Respondents found that the primary production in the EU and the logistics and storage to be competitive in a global world, but not the commercialisation of value-added products produced from renewable biological resources and EU measures for market development, harmonisation and standardisation in the field of bio-based industries. Basic research and investments of the private sector were seen as a strong points whereas the collaboration between stakeholders along value and supply chains, EU-wide coordination of applied research and technology development and investment of the public sector in research and innovation related to bio-based industries were seen as weak points.

Timeline key events:

2012: European Bioeconomy Strategy: Innovating for Sustainable Growth

2012: EIP –AGRI kicked off

2013: Bioeconomy panel to support interactions between different policy areas, sectors and stakeholders in the bioeconomy

2013: Bio-based industries, towards a public-private partnership under Horizon 2020.

4.1.3. Period FP8: H2020 (2014 – 2020)

Total framework budget 79 bln€ of which 3.85 bln – 4.52 – 7 bln (5% - 9%) related to bioeconomy

The successful research innovations in the domain of the EU bioeconomy did not receive sufficient follow up in the rest of society according to the Report on the European Commission's public on-line consultation from 2013. In order to put more efforts in achieving a bioeconomy in Europe the Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking (BBI JU) was established in 2014. The BBI JU is a public-private partnership aiming at increasing investment in the development of a sustainable bio-based industry sector in Europe. Its main objectives are:

- Demonstrate technologies that enable new chemical building blocks, new materials, and new consumer products from European biomass, which replace the need for fossil-based inputs;
- Develop business models that integrate economic actors along the value chain from supply of biomass to biorefinery plants to consumers of bio-based materials, chemicals and fuels, including through creating new cross-sector interconnections and supporting cross-industry clusters; and

Set-up flagship biorefinery plants that deploy the technologies and business models for bio-based materials, chemicals and fuels and demonstrate cost and performance improvements to levels that are competitive with fossil-based alternatives.

In November 2017 the EU reviewed the 2012 Bioeconomy strategy. The strategy identified five objectives to which the strategy and its action plan were to contribute: (1) ensuring food security, (2) managing natural resources sustainably, (3) reducing dependence on non-renewable resources, (4) mitigating and adapting to climate change, and (5) creating jobs and maintaining EU competitiveness. These five objectives were addressed via the strategy's Action Plan that focused on 3 areas of action with a total of 12 actions, subdivided into 54 sub-actions.

4.1.4. Main findings of the Research and Innovation review

“The 2012 EU Bioeconomy Strategy and Action Plan is delivering on key actions in the Action Plan. It has successfully mobilised R&I funding, in particular through a doubling of the EU R&I funding dedicated to the bioeconomy under Horizon 2020, and it has fostered R&I investments in Member States. It has also delivered on standards for bio-based products and supported private investment with major deliverables such as the launch of the BioBased Industries Joint Undertaking.

The opportunities that the bioeconomy offers and the importance of Bioeconomy Strategy coordination are increasingly recognised by EU Member States and regions.

The overall objectives of the 2012 EC Bioeconomy Strategy have been taken up in numerous national and regional bioeconomy strategies developed since 2012 in the EU and globally. However, there is still room for further development in Member States, and also the potential contribution of cities to the bioeconomy remains largely unexploited.

Further mobilisation of investments is still needed, which requires a stable regulatory environment. Existing and new technologies and demonstrators need to be up-scaled and rolled out. Especially private investment in integrated bio-refineries, which are capital intensive and are associated with high technological and market risks, require specific support and a stable regulatory environment.

Policy coherence needs to be better addressed, as well as the design and implementation of the Strategy and its Action Plan. The review demonstrates that there is insufficient correspondence between the strategic objectives in the Strategy and the actions of the Action Plan that were designed to achieve these objectives. Furthermore, objectives and actions lack 'SMART' targets. Combined with an insufficient assessment and monitoring framework, this hampered the achievement of results, in particular regarding policy coherence and synergies.

The current policy context highlights the need for a sustainable, circular bioeconomy. The policy context in which the bioeconomy operates has changed significantly since 2012, with EU and global policy developments such as Circular Economy, Energy Union, the Paris Agreement and the Sustainable Development Goals. In consequence, the concept of a sustainable, circular bioeconomy is being proposed by various stakeholders. The scope of

the 2012 Strategy and Action Plan and the relevance and focus of its objectives and actions have to be looked at in light of these developments.

Better monitoring and assessment frameworks are needed to assess progress. As sustainability in terms of production and consumption is core to the bioeconomy strategy, better understanding is necessary of the prospective development of biomass supply and demand, to ensure that the bioeconomy operates within the limits of the biosphere, while providing optimum social and economic gains. Indicators to assess progress can be based on an internationally shared monitoring and assessment framework that is in development for the Sustainable Development Goals, complemented with other appropriate indicators.”

R&I has become a priority for many European regions

“Existing evidence³¹ shows that a substantial number of regions having included bioeconomy-related priorities in their Research and Innovation Strategies for Smart Specialisation (RIS3). These Strategies are a funding pre-condition for EU cohesion policy, in particular for the research and innovation priority under the ERDF for which EUR 41 billion have been allocated for all areas. Out of 210 analysed territorial units (EU regions and countries) by a recent study²⁶, 207 have included bioeconomy-related aspects in their 2014-2020 RIS3 and related documents suggesting that also significant financial support will be made available from the ERDF. However, the study also shows that a large number of regions have a low level of maturity (35.7%) and cannot fully exploit the potential of the bioeconomy on their own. In addition, only a few cities have been identified that have bioeconomy-related priorities in their policies, despite the potential off municipal bio-waste for nutrient recovery, bio-based products and energetic use.”

4.2. Bioeconomy Policy Frameworks

On global, European, national and regional levels, policies regarding the bioeconomy have been set. BLOOM interacts with these frameworks through stakeholder management, and will therefore impact and be impacted by the boundaries they set, especially on regional level. To understand the possible effects of these impacts, and serve as a guide during co-creation workshops, this chapter aims to give an overview of the most relevant policies.

4.2.1. EU Grand Challenges Horizon 2020

At the start of the second decade of the 21st century, Europe faced a series of crucial challenges: low growth, insufficient innovation, and a diverse set of environmental and social challenges. The solutions to all of these problems are linked: it is precisely by addressing its environmental and social challenges that Europe will be able to boost productivity, generate long-term growth and secure its place in the new world order. The OECD (2011) has acknowledged that ‘green and growth can go hand-in-hand’. The United Nations, too, has observed that there is no inescapable trade-off between environmental sustainability and economic progress: the greening of economies creates growth and employment (UNEP, 2011). In the same vein, the European Commission published the

communication *GDP and beyond — Measuring progress in a changing world* (EC, 2009a) and is pursuing sustainable and inclusive growth through Europe 2020.

The following challenges have been distinguished:

- Health, demographic change and wellbeing;
- Food security, sustainable agriculture and forestry, marine and maritime and inland water research, and the bioeconomy;
- Secure, clean and efficient energy;
- Smart, green and integrated transport;
- Climate action, environment, resource efficiency and raw materials;
- Europe in a changing world - inclusive, innovative and reflective societies;
- Secure societies - protecting freedom and security of Europe and its citizens.

4.2.2. UN Sustainable Development Goals

On 25 September 2015, the United Nations General Assembly formally adopted the universal, integrated and transformative [2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development](#), along with a set of 17 SDGs and 169 associated targets.

The adoption of the 2030 Agenda and its SDGs represent a change of paradigm of the international policies on development cooperation. The EU has committed to implement the SDGs both in its internal and external policies. The following SDGs are relevant as Framework for the Bloom approach:

Goal 2: End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition, and promote sustainable agriculture

The EU approach focuses on four strategic priorities:

- Supporting agricultural growth in developing countries, with a focus on small-scale farmers.
- Promoting sustainable agricultural practices.
- Fighting undernutrition/stunting.
- Strengthening resilience to climatic, economic and political crisis of the most vulnerable populations.

Goal 8: Promote sustained, inclusive and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment and decent work for all

The EU development cooperation policy: the Agenda for Change focuses on inclusive and sustainable growth for human development as one of its priorities in particular in those sectors that have stronger multiplier impact on developing countries' economies, notably sustainable agriculture and energy.

Goal 9: Build resilient infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrialization and foster innovation

Blending, which combines EU grants with loans or other public and private funding, is increasingly supportive of actions on infrastructure which have a multiplier effect on

sustainable development in partner countries. EU actions are geared towards inclusive and sustainable growth and economic integration, building on partner countries' comparative advantages in the manufacturing or services sectors.

Goal 12: Ensure sustainable consumption and production patterns

The EU promotes for example responsible supply chains and responsible business practices of European companies in developing countries. The EU also promotes the transition to an inclusive green economy that generates growth and creates decent jobs in partner countries, notably through the Switch to Green initiative.

Goal 13: Take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts

The EU has been at the forefront of international efforts towards the Paris global climate agreement. The EU is stepping up its international climate diplomacy to maintain the political momentum and support other countries in the implementation of the Paris Agreement and their climate plans.

4.2.3. Missions - Horizon Europe

The future EU framework for knowledge and innovation will be built on the Mazzucato (2018) publications about mission oriented innovation policies. Missions provide a way to harness and direct the power of research and innovation, not only stimulate economic activity and growth, but also to find innovative solutions to the most pressing challenges of our time (EU publication, Mazzucato, 2018).

The issue of public engagement and missions is crucial because of the symbiotic nature of the relationship between the two. Missions provide a straightforward explanation to the public of how diverse, and sometimes difficult to understand, developments in research and innovation can contribute to a better society. In addition, the potential impact of missions is much higher when they inspire and engage widespread support (Mazzucato, 2018).

4.2.4. EU policies and Frameworks

In February 2012, the European Commission submitted its strategy and action plan for a sustainable bioeconomy in Europe, “Innovating for Sustainable Growth: A Bioeconomy for Europe,” to the European Parliament (EC, 2012). This strategy is Europe’s response to key environmental challenges the world is facing today. It’s meant to reduce the dependence on natural resources, transform manufacturing and promote sustainable production of renewable resources, while growing new jobs and industries (Figure 5).

Figure 5 EU strategy (2012)

The strategy is structured around three pillars:

- Investments in research, innovation and skills;
- Reinforced policy interaction and stakeholder engagement;
- Enhancement of markets and competitiveness

The Action Plan focuses on cross-sectorial and multi-disciplinary approaches by developing Joint Programming Initiatives (JPIs), ERA-Net activities, by supporting bio-clusters and Knowledge and Innovation Communities (KICs) and by establishing a Bioeconomy Panel to support synergies and coherence between different policy areas and a Bioeconomy Observatory to gather data and indicators to assess the progress (Scarlat et al, 2015). The strategy is also affected by a number of other ongoing or recent EU policies. We mention here the action plan on circular economy where also a new dedicated plastics strategy is being prepared, the promotion of climate SMART agriculture, the Digital agenda for technological development and innovation and the bioeconomy stakeholders manifesto.

The bioeconomy strategy is probably most affected by the Renewable Energy Directive and the Emission Trading System (ETS).

The European Commission is currently working on a new EU Bioeconomy Policy and Strategy, expected to be launched in October 2018. The strategies will be developed towards a sustainable circular bioeconomy, influenced by the concepts of Circular Economy, Paris Agreement and the UN Sustainable Development Goals. More investment and coherence will be needed, alongside better monitoring and assessment and improving the connection between supply and demand.

4.2.5. National Policy frameworks

16 Member States have National Bioeconomy Strategies. Some countries (Austria, Germany) are developing new strategies. We will describe shortly two strategies as good examples, which are also relevant to the BLOOM hubs:

Finland

According to national Bioeconomy Strategy Finland will reduce its dependence on fossil natural resources, prevent biodiversity loss and create new economic growth and jobs in line with the principles of sustainable development. The objective of the Bioeconomy Strategy is to push economic output up to EUR 100 billion by 2025 and to create 100,000 new jobs. By 2025 Finland is expecting bioeconomy to provide a turnover of 60 bn euro, share of employment 13 % and share of exports 26 % (speech of Waldemar Kutt, Biostep meeting, march 2018).

The Netherlands

In the Netherlands, the first policy framework at national level was being published in 2007: 'The vision of the National Government on biobased economy and the energy transition – close the value chain', focussing on a bio-based economy aiming at using optimal value in combination with a sustainable energy supply service:

- Energy savings of 2% per year (Regeerakkoord, 2007)
- Growing use of non-fossil energy resources, 20% sustainable energy in 2020: solar, wind, waterpower and biomass.
- 30% reduction of CO₂, in 2020.

The national government started a working program on "Schoon en Zuinig" "clean and economical", focussing low energy use and alternative energy supply in specific economic sectors. Also a knowledge and innovation program has been set up (2011), which resulted in an Innovation Contract on Green Growth: from biomass to business (2012), to support the R&D between knowledge institutes and companies, focussing on innovations, new business development and start-ups.

"Biomassa 2030 (2016)" is a strategic vision and route for the use and valorization of biomass, to contribute optimally to the policy goals on food, energy, climate, mobility, biobased and circular economy. Biomass will be seen in the context of climate problem, renewable resources and circular economy. This vision focusses on:

- Enlarging the sustainable supply of biomass: improve collection of rest streams towards new commodities, enlarge the production of current biomass and on waste land and aquatic biomass.
- Optimization of utilization of crops and components.
- New applications of biomass in a broad pallet of biochemicals and biopolymers.
- Investment in new production capacity, in research and development and in new technologies: first of a kind fabrics, biorefineries, alternative protein production.
- Sustainability in the production chain and waste management.

4.2.6. Regional Policy Frameworks

For the regional implementation the EU developed the RIS3 framework: regional innovation strategies for SMART specialization. Regions are challenged and forced to make strategic choices for specific sectors, which fit to the characteristics of their economies and environment, physically as well as culturally. SWOTs have been applied and regions have chosen their profiles, strategies and plans and organisational structures for implementation. Many regions have mentioned the bioeconomy as one of the main drivers for regional innovation and growth. Within the bioeconomy many routes are possible, depending on the combination of availability and components of the regional biomass and the existing industries in which the biomass components can be valorized.

4.2.7. Bioeconomy Stakeholder Panel

The Bioeconomy stakeholder panel has originally been set up in 2013. The membership of the Panel was renewed in 2016 to strengthen the diversity in stakeholders' representation. The panel represents different groups: business and primary producers, policy-makers and public administrations, scientists and researchers and civil society organisations. The Panel has an important say in the new European Bioeconomy Strategy. The input will be based on the reflection and discussions on the uptake of the bioeconomy in Europe. The Panel has developed a bioeconomy stakeholder Manifesto signed by many stakeholders in May 2016. The Manifesto recognises the opportunities and challenges of developing the bioeconomy and provides inspiration to stakeholders, regions and Member States, at various stages of development of their bioeconomy strategies, as well as to the EU as a whole. The Guiding Principles for Development of the bioeconomy of the Manifesto, addressing Societal and Environmental Challenges are:

1. Resource use within the limits of the planet
2. Mitigating Climate Change
3. Producing for people
4. Sustainable Management of Resources Facilitating Innovations and Business Opportunities

In order to facilitate innovations and business opportunities the bioeconomy needs:

1. A stable and predictable legal framework

2. Cooperation between sectors (production of biomass, processing and application in industrial sectors) and along value-chains creates synergies and critical mass
3. A long-term Research and Innovation Agenda
4. Recognize the importance of regional strategies and rural renaissance

To reach these goals the following actions are defined:

1. Education, Training and Skills
2. Open Science and Research Programme Alignment
3. Bridging the Innovation Gap by Public-Private Partnership
4. Embracing the Circular Economy
5. Strengthening the Regional Bioeconomy and Inter-Regio
6. Raising Public Awareness and Improving Communication
7. Establishing a Socio-Economic Monitoring System
8. Promoting Biomass Availability
9. Research and assessment of biomass potentials

BLOOM aligns with the actions defined in the Bioeconomy Stakeholder Panel. Especially point 1, 4, 5 and 6 are core goals in the project.

5. Concerns about the bioeconomy development

Development of the bioeconomy is a societal transition. New technologies are developed and implemented and new organisational structures may evolve. Undoubtedly this leads to questions about the sustainability of these developments. Furthermore, there are ethical concerns around some of the new technologies and developments, as well as questions about the impact of their implementation. These issues concern all hubs, and are therefore not specifically hub-related, and are raised and discussed in the BLOOM co-creation workshops. Issues that may arise were discussed in the BLOOM meeting in December 2017:

1. Genetic Modification
2. Land Use Change, direct and indirect, and effect on greenhouse gas emissions
3. Food versus fuel discussion
4. Sustainability of agriculture including fertilizers and crop protection
5. Economies of scale and local impacts of new bioeconomy production chains
6. Circularity and safety of new production systems.

Other issues may arise during the co-creation workshops and outreach activities, and if so they will be addressed by the BLOOM project.

5.1. GM technology

Genetic modification (GM) points to a variety of techniques to influence the properties of plants, animals and micro-organisms by changing their genetic material. Genetic modification of crops can be used to improve their resistance to for instance pests and drought, and especially outside Europe farmers have widely adopted GM technology. Within Europe the use of GM for crops is controversial. There are many processes within the bioeconomy that do not use genetically modified organisms. However, in the bioeconomy, GM can also be used to change the properties of micro-organisms, for instance to increase the speed at which they produce certain target molecules, or to produce a special product. Adapted yeasts are already widely used in many processes in the pharma industry and also in some food/feed industry processes. The difference with GM on crops is that the micro-organisms, yeasts and enzymes are used in a contained production system within a factory/plant and are not expected to enter the environment. Nevertheless there are concerns, for instance on the perception of safety: some people fear that modified organisms can escape from their containers and infect / contaminate other organisms. Pointing at proof of safety based on rational reasoning does not always take away these concerns. Some companies, like NatureWorks, (NatureWorks 2019) therefore also market GM free bio-based products or bioplastics, hereby offering (besides their standard GM-product) consumers a choice.

5.2. Land use change

Additional demand for feedstock, especially for transportation fuels and bioenergy may lead to direct and indirect land use change. When biofuels/bioenergy feedstock is produced on existing agricultural land, the demand for food and feed crops remains, and may lead to

someone producing more food and feed somewhere else. This can imply land use change (by changing e.g. forest into agricultural land), which implies that a substantial amount of CO₂ emissions are released into the atmosphere. The use of residue streams for these applications can reduce land use change. Furthermore, the demand for biomaterials feedstock is at maximum only a fraction of the demand for transportation fuels feedstock, and also first generation feedstock like corn, sugarbeet or sugarcane can be a sustainable choice for the chemical industry (Dammer et al. 2019). Additionally, multiple use of crops, multicropping systems and optimal valorisation of side streams can help to reduce the pressure on land. Consumer product choices influence the demand for certain feedstock and are therefore relevant to discuss.

5.3. Food versus fuel discussion

The discussion on food versus fuel is very much in line with the discussion on land use change. Demand for feedstock for biofuels may raise food prices and may impact especially the poor. High food prices are caused by a number of factors, and there is no scientific agreement on the exact impact of biofuel production on food prices, but many people are concerned about the effect the increasing demand on biomass feedstock may have. On the other hand, multiple outlets for agricultural production, food/feed, biomaterials or biofuels, can be beneficial for farmers and lead to increased production of biomass (Kline et al 2017), and thus to increased availability of biomass feedstock, also for other applications. The maximum demand for feedstock for materials use is much easier to bring in line with the demand for food production. Cascading use of biomass (smart design of a biorefinery process leading to efficient use of biomass), multiple use of crops and use of side streams can help to reduce the demand for feedstock. Also, reducing food waste, a subject that may be well recognisable for the general European public, helps to decrease the pressure on biomass demand.

5.4. Sustainability of agriculture

Sustainability of agriculture in general has many facets, economic (agriculture should be profitable in order to be sustained), social (relating to workers and surrounding communities) and environmental. Environmental sustainability in agriculture means good stewardship of the natural systems and resources that farms rely on. This involves sustaining a healthy soil, wise management of water, working towards minimal pollution and promoting biodiversity. The circular use of fertilisers, especially phosphate, which is finite, and the application of sustainable crop protection methods are important points of concern. These issues are important for food and feed production as well as for the wider bioeconomy, including biofuels, bioenergy and biomaterials.

5.5. Scale and local impact

Biomass production is more or less evenly distributed across the whole of Europe. This raises questions as to what is the optimum scale of production facilities. Agriculture and the subsequent production chain for food/feed and non-food products can supply jobs in rural

areas. On the other hand there may be concerns about increasing pressure of transport, smell, noise and other impacts on the local environment as production facilities grow.

5.6. Circularity and safety

Besides sustainable production, a circular bioeconomy would want to optimally use waste streams. This raises questions about the safety of circular production systems. For instance the use of human excreta for fertilising crops is an interesting concept to improve the circularity of minerals, but raises questions about the presence of pharmaceutical residues in these streams and efficient ways to remove them. Next to this, bio-based materials can replace fossil based materials, that contain components which are under suspicion, such as bisphenol-A. Safe and efficient use and recycling of bio-based materials is key to the development of a sustainable bioeconomy. Citizens play an important role in the purchase, use and end-of-life routes of biomaterials and thus need to be more aware of the pros and cons of the various options in order to make well informed choices in line with their own values.

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